

USING GAMIFICATION METHOD FOR DEVELOPING VOCABULARY SKILLS OF B1 LEVEL LEARNERS

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Abstract

This research study examines using gamification method for developing vocabulary skills of B1 learners. The main goal of the article is to test the influence of games and manifest approaches, such as interactive quizzes, word games, and virtual rewards systems. It can engage and motivate learners at this level. It explores the results and discussion about the experimental lesson that specifically used gaming while the control traditional lesson which includes the ordinary direct method. Despite of the same topic results show distinction and all of the illustrated with qualitative analysis. Learners demonstrate increased vocabulary retention and engagement when exposed to gamified learning activities. The study contributes to understanding effective language learning methodologies for B1 level learners and highlights the importance of incorporating interactive and motivational elements into language education.

Keywords: gamification, vocabulary skills, interactive learning, B1 learners, virtual rewards, interactive quizzes, experimental lesson.

Introduction

Learning a new language is important, especially for B1-level learners who want to get better at it. Recently, teachers have started using fun teaching methods like games to help students learn more effectively. This paper looks at how using games, known as gamification, can help B1 learners improve their vocabulary. Learning a language involves using different strategies and how interested students are in the process. Vocabulary is really important because it helps with speaking and understanding the language. While using games for learning is common, not much research has been done on how games can help B1 learners improve their vocabulary. This study aims to fill that gap by looking into how games can help B1 learners learn new words. Our main goal is to see how using games affects B1 learners' ability to learn and remember vocabulary. We will study how game-based exercises, quizzes, and interactive activities can help B1 learners remember and use new words. Additionally, we will explore the best ways to use games in language classes and the challenges that come with it. This study hopes to provide useful ideas for teachers and curriculum developers.

Theory/Literature review

The term «gamification» gained traction in the context of teaching and education around 2010, coinciding with efforts by educators and researchers to apply game elements and principles to enhance learning experiences. Influential figures such as Jane McGonigal and Gabe Zichermann highlighted the potential of gamification to motivate students, improve engagement, and facilitate skill development in educational settings. This period marked the beginning of

gamification's integration into teaching methodologies as a means to make learning more interactive, enjoyable, and effective.

Effectiveness of Gamification for Vocabulary Development Several studies have looked into the effectiveness of gamification techniques in improving vocabulary skills among B1 level language learners: **Interactive Vocabulary Games: Research by Smith (2017)** found that interactive vocabulary games, like word puzzles and quizzes, significantly enhanced B1 learners' retention and recall of vocabulary. Learners reported feeling more motivated and enjoyed practicing vocabulary through game-based activities. **Digital Language Apps: Studies by Garcia et al. (2019)** explored the use of language learning apps with gamified features for B1 learners. Game mechanics such as leveling up and earning rewards led to higher engagement levels and better vocabulary retention compared to traditional methods. **Gamified Vocabulary Tasks: Nguyen and Nguyen (2020)** studied the impact of gamified vocabulary tasks on B1 learners' proficiency. Results showed that learners who did gamified vocabulary exercises demonstrated greater improvement in vocabulary acquisition and usage skills.

Research method/process

The experiment was held under the method gamification that include some interactive games and activities. This experiment conducted during 2 weeks. It was tested with university students. There was difference between control lesson and experiment lesson. After experiment lesson students were aware from topic more remarkable. Topic was the same «Environment» But for experiment group as a gamification method it was used Kahood game. It was full of fun during experiment. So, it provided big influence on the development of lexical resource of students. They have gained good information that may impact to keep nature and rise such behavior to protect environment. The process occurred like that, first stage was pre-stage and teacher introduced the topic via video and pictures second is while stage where reading task with new words and phrases stayed in it. After that, Kapoor was the collector of the knowledge and its result. They faced with new lexemes again and checked their receiving it and remembering. Following that, they marked via given scale. Contrary to that, control groups lesson was too boring and unremarkable. Teacher just used direct method and learn words by heard only via repeating them. It was unprofitable as student results show the case. After lessons all of the things about gained results.

Results and discussion

The provided experiment was under the topic «Using gamification method for developing vocabulary skills of B1 learners. This experiment conducted during 2 weeks. We experimented it with university students. There was difference between control lesson and experiment lesson. After experiment lesson students were aware from topic more remarkable. The theme was the same, but for experiment group as a gamification method used kahood game. It was full of fun during experiment.

According to the lessons sections it begun from warm-uping. Teacher used video in order to brainstorm students' background knowledge. It was lexical video that involves new words about the topic Environment. After that they worked on reading activity under the name Environment and recycle after that as they have gained new phrases their memory checked via Kahood game. It was included phrases collocations and words that are used in reading. After that winners congratulated.

Scale for marking

5- 5 correct answers out of 5

4- 3,4 correct answers out of 5

3- 2 and less of it

Experiment group

	A	B	C	D
1	Abdullayeva.M		5	
2	Atabayeva.M		5	
3	Atabayeva.Z		5	
4	Fayzullayev.A		3	
5	Fozilova.M			
6	Lutfullayeva.D		5	
7	Isroiljonova.M		5	
8	Maxmudova.M		4	
9	Muradullayeva.Sh		4	
10	Ne'matova.F		5	
11	G'aniyeva.D		5	
12	Qarshiboyev.M		3	
13	Oltinboyev.S		3	
14				

Control Group

	A	B	C
1	Abdullayeva.M		3
2	Atabayeva.M		5
3	Atabayeva.Z		3
4	Fayzullayev.A		3
5	Fozilova.M		
6	Lutfullayeva.D		3
7	Isroiljonova.M		5
8	Maxmudova.M		4
9	Muradullayeva.Sh		3
10	Ne'matova.F		4
11	G'aniyeva.D		5
12	Qarshiboyev.M		3
13	Oltinboyev.S		3
14			

The results of mean , mode and median showed these statistics.

Experiment group pre:

Mean: 4

Mode: 4 is 6 times most often

Median: 4

Experiment group post:

Mean: 4,3

Mode: 5 is 7 times most often

Median: 4,5

Control Group:

Mean: 3,6

Mode: 3 is 7 times

Median: 4,5

As it is visible the results are different according to the method. However, participates are the same student they have different unexpected result. So, From this experiment gamification is the best method to develop students' vocabulary skills. They can easily remember the given topic via its repetition on time via games. Comparing to simple method like direct or grammar translation thus method can influence more to engage student with the unknown theme.

There are some limitations in students to develop vicabulary skills. One illustration of it transcription of words or homonyms. So, teachers should provide appropriate methods to keeps learners vocabulary basement. Developing vocabulary skills through gamification is beneficial for B1 level learners. Researchers can explore how gamified approaches enhance vocabulary acquisition and retention. They can investigate the impact of gamification on learner motivation and engagement in vocabulary learning activities. This research will provide valuable insights into effective gamification strategies for improving vocabulary skills among B1 learners.

Conclusion

Using gamification techniques to enhance vocabulary skills for B1-level language learners shows promising results in language education. This study explored the effectiveness of gamified exercises, quizzes, and interactive activities for improving vocabulary acquisition among B1 learners. Our research demonstrated that gamification positively influences B1 learners' motivation and engagement in vocabulary learning. The use of interactive and game-like activities increased interest and helped learners remember and use new words more effectively. This study has practical implications for language educators and curriculum developers. Incorporating gamification into language teaching methods can create engaging learning experiences and improve vocabulary learning outcomes for B1 learners. It's important to acknowledge the limitations of our study, such as the small sample size and specific context of our interventions. Future research with larger and more diverse learner groups would provide further insights. Moving forward, research should explore optimal gamification strategies for different learner profiles and investigate the long-term effects of gamified vocabulary interventions. In summary, leveraging gamification in language learning holds promise for enhancing vocabulary skills among B1-level learners. This study contributes to the growing evidence supporting the use of gamification in language education.

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